

DEVELOPMENT OF NEW GENERATION FOOD SUPPLEMENTS

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Abstract

Nowadays, we see more and more products in the functional food market that are high in protein and fiber and can help you lose weight by triggering a meal. Dietary supplements are increasingly consumed not only by professional athletes but also by consciously eating hobby athletes.

Consumers in this category are more open than average to novelties, so the range of ingredients in dietary supplements is constantly expanding with ingredients that have not been used in this field before.

These products are usually made from milk, mostly on a whey protein basis. Although they are being offered with more and more flavors, the products are soon becoming unanimous for their consumers. In addition, they are not solutions for people who are sensitive to lactose or milk protein. Accordingly, we would like to develop a milk-free, fruit- and / or vegetable-based beverage powder in the product range, which contains plant extracts like brown seaweed and cactus fruit. In addition, we want to use a variety of plant-specific functional ingredients that are highly suited to the active athlete's lifestyle and are high in plant-derived polyphenols. A high polyphenol content, a varied and balanced diet, a proper lifestyle and careful exercise can help the consumers to improve their sports performance.

A fruit / vegetable-based, lactose-free beverage powder that fits well into a weight-loss diet can be a great help for health-conscious people who need a special diet and want to lose weight. The presence of real fruits or vegetables in powdered form in the product provides significant added value compared to the flavors found in other products, so we think, that conscious consumers will be willing to buy at a higher price.

In summary, we successfully fulfilled our goal, and implemented the formulated sensory and content requirements. Our partners showed growing interest of these products, both during and after development. The developed products stand their ground on their own, and can be considered a great starting point for future, even to meet latent needs.

In addition to the knowledge we have already acquired, our plans include getting to know other plant active ingredients for health and creating new products based on it. Also included are plant protein-based spoonable and skin care products.